

PUBLISHER CORRECTION OPEN

Publisher Correction: Historical predictability of rainfall erosivity: a reconstruction for monitoring extremes over Northern Italy (1500–2019)

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npj Climate and Atmospheric Science (2021)4:10; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-021-00164-z>

Correction to: *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* **3**, 46; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-020-00144-9>, published online 23 November 2020.

The original version of this Article contained an error in Fig. 5, in which the upper and bottom panels were incorrectly labelled 'B' and 'A', respectively, instead of the correct 'A' and 'B', and the figure included redundant labels 'C' and 'D'. The correct version of Fig. 5 is:

Fig. 5

which replaces the previous incorrect version:

Fig. 5

The first sentence of the second paragraph of the Methods originally incorrectly read ‘(R)USLE model¹⁰³ appears in the following form.’ The correct version cites references ‘103,104’ instead of ‘103’.

The third sentence of the final paragraph of the Methods originally incorrectly read ‘The Kling–Gupta index ($-\infty < KGE \leq 1^{117}$) was used as an efficiency measure, with $KGE > -0.41$ indicating that a model improves upon the means of observations as a benchmark predictor^{118,119}’. The correct version cites reference ‘119’ instead of ‘118,119’.

As a consequence of these errors, current citations in the text to references [105–118] were previously incorrectly numbered [104–117] respectively.

Finally, the third sentence of the ‘Numerical and categorical dependent variables’ section of the Methods originally incorrectly read ‘A categorical variable, the annual severity storm index sum (ASSIS), was derived from Diodato et al.⁵⁶ to overcome the lack of

historical information about rain intensity’. The correct version cites reference ‘66’ instead of ‘56’.

This has been corrected in both the PDF and HTML versions of the Article.

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